

Smart buildings, Comfort, Indoor Air Quality, Load Flexibility... Is it all possible?

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- What is a building? What do people expect from a building?
 - Shelter, security, living space, privacy & comfort
 - Thermal comfort
 - Indoor air quality
- How is our technosociety asking buildings to behave?
 - Provide healthy indoor conditions
 - NZEB, +EB, PED,...
 - Shift loads, Balance the grid, provide ancillary services...
 - Support the deployment of EVs
 - We almost ask buildings to achieve Peace in the world

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Is it possible?

- In short: YES
- Longer Answer
 - Technically complex
 - Very atomized sector, with millions of assets and sub-optimal quality of control systems
 - Requires a large investment
 - ...

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LESOSAI 5. Mode de Emploi. 2002.
<https://docplayer.fr/57528916-Lesosai-5-calcul-du-bilan-thermique-d-une-construction-sia-380-1-en832-et-minergie.html>

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- Transmission losses/Gains
- Solar Heat Gains
- Ventilation Mass transfer
- Heat input/extraction to keep thermal balance

Geometry Windows Insulation Building Climate Energy

number of floors: 2

west facade: 52,0 m² south facade: 52,0 m²

height (without roof): 5,2 m

width: 10,0 m length: 10,0 m

roof ridge: north-south-direction, east-west-direction

S/V-ratio in 1/m: 0,78

orientation: deviation from south direction WEST 0° EAST

building data:

ground area	100,0	m ²
heated floor	160,0	m ²
total volume	520,0	m ³
air volume	416,0	m ³

Info

University of Siegen

Division of Building Physics & Solar Energy

CASAnova

(Version 3.3.03)

An Educational Software for Heating and Cooling Energy Demand as well as the Temperature Behaviour in Buildings

Developed by:
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OK

Energy Balance of a Building

- Old building (Zagreb)
 - Demand: ~500kWh (~90% Heating)
 - ~60% Transmission Losses
- New building
 - Demand: ~170kWh (~75% Heating)
 - ~50% Transmission Losses
- Evolution
 - Demand reduced to about 1/3
 - Insulation close to adiabatic conditions

EURIMA, U-VALUES FOR BETTER ENERGY PERFORMANCE OF BUILDINGS, 2007

- Avoid fossil fuels
- PV as potentially carbon free energy source
 - Intermittent
- Electric vehicles as a large energy sink
 - Source of congestion
- Batteries
 - (some) Detached housing
 - Large assets

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Is it all possible?

- NZEB, +EB
 - Optimal envelope
 - Electrification. Heat Pumps (with very large PV)
 - Intermittent PV production ?
 - Optimization of HVAC control
- Shift loads, Balance the grid, provide ancillary services...(Keeping same level of service: indoor temperature)
 - Need to pre-charge inertial systems
 - Consume before to avoid consumption at a certain moment
 - Avoid excessive temperature swings

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Key fields of research

- Occupant-focused
- Occupancy and usage models
- Probabilistic approach to load optimization
- Decision-making processes
- Aggregation/Pooling

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- Occupant-focused
 - Avoid HVAC if nobody is present
 - Performance-based control
 - Dual setpoint systems:
 - Setpoint: Periods with occupants & periods with “free” energy
 - Setback: Other periods. Lower consumption, but easy transition to setpoint values if occupancy is detected/forecasted

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• Occupancy and usage models

- Likelihood of having 300pax in Bol on 19 June?
 - **High** (1-year auto-regression)
- Likelihood of having 100pax in the keynote?
 - **Low** (I'm not Santamouris)
- EV charge profiles (did I go to the supermarket today?)

- Probabilistic approach to load optimization
 - Building commits X flexibility @ 15:00 - 17:00
 - Probability to activate flexibility
 - 30%: $0.2 * X$
 - 0.5%: X
 - Need to “prepare” for interruption (before 15:00)
 - 100% * X-Need to “recover” after flexibility (after 17:00)
 - 30%: $0.2 * X$
 - 0.5%: X

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Higher setpoint in the morning to allow for flexibility

Standard, Schedule-based control

Increased load (hopefully with near-free energy)

100%

Flexibility order @12-14h

Committed flexibility 100%

Delivered: 0.5-30%

Rebound effect 0.5-30%

- Decision-making processes
 - Reward all stakeholders (I will not flexibilize if I'm not rewarded)
 - Coding of optimal policies (trading between confort/service level and energy costs)
 - Definition of acceptable service level (I'm Ok as long as my EV is at 80% at 6AM)

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$$R_k = \sum \alpha_{q_i} * q_{i,k} + \sum \alpha_{c_i} * c_{i,k} \quad (1)$$

$$\sum \alpha_{q_i} * q_i = \alpha_{q_{thc}} * q_{thc} + \alpha_{q_t} * q_t + \alpha_{q_h} * q_h + \alpha_{q_{iaq}} * q_{iaq} + \alpha_{q_{vc}} * q_{vc} \quad (3a)$$

Devil is in the Alfas

$$\sum \alpha_{c_i} * c_{i,k} = \alpha_{c_{ec}} * c_{ec} + \alpha_{c_{wts}} * c_{wts} + \alpha_{c_{pe}} * c_{pe} + \alpha_{c_{ghg}} * c_{ghg} \quad (3b)$$

- Aggregation/Pooling
 - One building/asset
 - Small load
 - Uncertain Performance
 - Large group of buildings (i.e. All hotels in Split distribution área)
 - Large load (can bid in the flexibility market)
 - Predictable performance
- Likelihood of flexibility potential -> ~100%
- Amalgamation of flexibility curves in individual assets to “design” response curves with potentially any shape
 - Sharp initial response?
 - Avoid “rebound” effects
 - Soft, but longer flexibility
 - ...

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Advancing the role of Energy Communities by innovative Energy Management Systems

STUNNED aims to reduce the energy consumption of residential and industrial buildings. Therefore, these buildings and their users are brought together to form Energy Communities, which use renewable energies to balance energy supply and demand, ensure a stable and reliable electricity grid and consequently play a more active role in the energy market.

<https://stunned-project.eu/>

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